

**CRITICAL ASPECT OF VYADHIKSHAMTAV AND ITS ROLE IN PREVENTION OF
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18438002>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Anand Chamat^{*1}, Vd. Suryakant Dwivedi², Vd. Sneha Tiwairi. (2026). Critical Aspect of Vyadhikshamtav and Its Role In Prevention of Tuberculosis (Rajyakshma). World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(2), 367–370.

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Article Received on 30/12/2025

Article Revised on 20/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTRACT

Immunity plays a very important role in one's life. It not only helps to prevent the disease from occurring but also to cure it and diminish its harmful effects. It is proven that even after multiple exposure with several etiological factors, few people remain free from diseases or a particular disease, and if they become ill, they just have mild symptoms or get well soon. This ability to fight the disease is known as *vyadhikshamtav*, which in modern terms is known as immunity. In *Ayurveda*, *vyadhikshamtav* depends mainly on two factors – *Bala* and *Ojas*. Thus, we can see that *ayurvedic* treatment of several disorders includes medicine or food to increase one's *Bala* and *Ojas*. Tuberculosis is a life-threatening disorder, increasing continuously in India, which is compared with *Rajyakshma* in *Ayurveda*. There is a need for time for every medical science work closely for its prevention and treatment. Thus, an attempt is made to understand the critical aspect of *vyadhikshamtav*, Immunity, *Bala*, *Ojas*, and their importance in the prevention of *Rajyakshma* (Tuberculosis).

KEYWORDS: *Bala*, *Vyadhikshamtav*, *Ojas*, *Rajyakshma*, Tuberculosis, Immunity.**INTRODUCTION**

The immune system is described as a highly developed network of integrated bodily parts, including organs, tissues, cells, and cell products, to physiologically resist foreign agents or invaders^[1]. In *Ayurveda* Immunity is defined as *Vyadhikshamtav* but it refers to more than just immunity against a particular pathogen or illness, such as typhoid, measles, or rubella, for which contemporary medicine offers "immunisations". The term "*Vyadhikshamtava*" refers to a defense against the degradation of the *doshas* and *dhatu*s of the individual, as well as their proportion, interrelationship, and integrity. Thus, it helps in preventing the disease to occur and also reduces the ill effects of a disease. It is correlated with *Bala* and *Ojas*, two important factors in *Ayurveda*. *Rajyakshma*, also referred to as 'King Of All Disease', is caused by *Sahasa* (over effort), *Vegasandharana* (suppression of natural desires), *Kshaya* (depletion of tissue elements), and *vishamashana* (irregular & unsuitable nutrition), which lead to the vitiation of *tridosha* & *saptadhatu* and ultimately

Rajyakshma.^[2] It is correlated with pulmonary tuberculosis in modern medicine. Despite several preventative and therapeutic measures, TB is the most common cause of illness and mortality globally. TB is a chronic pulmonary and systemic disease caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. India has the highest prevalence of tuberculosis (TB) in the world, with an anticipated 26.9 lakh cases in 2019. It is estimated that 5.05 people per thousand in India have tuberculosis on average.^[3] Thus, here we are going to study the critical aspects of *Vyadhikshamtav* with *Bala* and *Ojas* and how they can help prevent Tuberculosis.

AIM

To study the critical aspects of *vyadhikshamtav* in special reference to *Bala*, *Ojas*, and immunity and its importance in the prevention of *Rajyakshma* (Tuberculosis).

OBJECTIVE

- 1) To study *Vyadhikshamtav* in modern parlance.
- 2) To study *Ojas* and *Bala*.

3) To study the role of *vyadhikshamtav* in the prevention of *Rajyakshma*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

As this study is a literature review based. Material has been collected from *Charak Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtang Hridaya*, *Madhav Nidana*, and Harrison Textbook of Medicine. Textbook of Pathology by Harsh Mohan, K. Sembulingam, Textbook of physiology and various articles and research available on Google Scholar, PubMed, Research Gate, etc.

LITERATURE VIEW

Vyadhikshamtav in Ayurveda

Vyadhikshamtava is the strength of the body, which either prevents the disease or counteracts the disease that already exists to keep our body healthy. Acharya Chakrapani Datta, give two divisions of this^[4] –

- (I) ***Vyadhi-balavirodhitvam***: It is the strength to reduce the severity of disease or to give strength to the body to fight against disease; this can be done by using *Naimittika Rasayana* and can be correlated with *Yuktikrita bala* or acquired immunity.
- (II) ***Vyadhi-utpadakapratibandhakatva***: It is the strength of the body to prevent the occurrence of a disease. It may be correlated with *Sahaja bala* or innate immunity.

For example, *Plasmodium Falciparum* is racial specific disease (will not affect Africans)^[5]

The concept of *vyadhikshamtav* can be understood by

- 1) *Vikarvighatbhava*
- 2) *Ojas*
- 3) *Bala*

Vikarvighatbhava- It can be defined as ‘when the body's resistant power is powerful enough to demolish the cause, diseases will not manifest themselves’^[6]

Ojas- *Ojas* is described as the essence of the *Saptadhatus*. It is located in the heart and is white, yellowish, and reddish in colour, or like the hue of ghee. It tastes like honey and has fried paddy-like aromas. According to *Acharya Charak*, *Ojas* is *Pranayatan*, which indicates that if *Ojas* is destroyed, humans will also perish. The term *Bala* is also used as synonyms of *ojas*.^[7]

Bala: It takes strength to engage in physical activity, combat, and overcome numerous ailments and their devastating effects. This depends on Physiological components as well as *Prakriti*. It is also known as ‘*Adhistana* (basis) for *Arogya*’. *Balam* is divided into three categories-

1. ***Sahaja Bala***: A *sahaja bala* is a quality that has existed in a person's body and mind since birth and is brought about by variables related to the parents, such as *rasa*, *rakta*, *virya*, and *ojas*. It grows together with the

development of *Dhatus* and is independent of all other factors.

2. ***Kalaja Bala***: This kind of *Bala* is influenced by seasonal characteristics and an individual's age. The *Sharira Bala* of an individual decreases in *Aadana Kala* and grows in *Visarga Kala*. *Dhatu kshaya*, which occurs in old age, causes a person's *Sharira bala* to decrease.

3. ***Yuktikrita bala***:- It is the body's acquired strength, which is obtained by healthy eating, exercise, rest, *rasayana*, and *vajikaran* treatments.

Immunity^[9]: Immunity is the body's ability to fend off harmful invaders. It is the body's capacity to fend off the admission of various alien entities, such as bacteria, viruses, poisonous compounds, etc. There are two types:

I. Innate immunity- It is also known as natural immunity or non-specific immunity, and is the body's innate ability to fight against viruses. When organisms enter the body, innate immunity kills them before any disease develops.

II. Acquired immunity- It is also known as specific immunity, and is the body's defence mechanism against a particular foreign substance, such as bacteria, viruses, poisons, vaccinations, or transplanted tissues.

Concept of Communicable / Contagious Disease^[10]

A specific infectious agent or its toxic by-product spreads from an infected person, animal, or reservoir to a susceptible host either directly or indirectly through an intermediary plant, animal, or human host, vector. This process is what causes contagious/ communicable diseases. *Aupsargika roga* is the term used by *Acharya Sushruta* to describe diseases that spread from one person to another due to intimate and frequent physical contact, *gatra samsparsha* (contact of limbs) like shaking hands, *nishwasa* (breathing or airborne), *sahabhajana* (eating from the same utensil), *saha shaiyasana* (sleeping in the same bed), and *vastra*. These transmission techniques are still applicable based on recent epidemiology data perspectives. According to *Acharya Sushrut*, *shosha* is created by consuming *Viprakrista Nidana*, while *Rajyakshma* eventually develops the illness after obtaining the *Sannikrista Nidana's Upasarga* (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*) organism. He said this without the influence of *Ritu* (appropriate season), *Beeja* (seed), *Kshetra* (field), *Ambu* (water), or time, a foetus cannot germinate and grow, and neither can a plant. The same principle can be used to generate infectious diseases. Among these four elements, *Kshetra* (Particular significance is given to the human body), *Beeja* (the infectious agent), *Ritu* (appropriate time permitting the best growth), and *Ambu* (nutritional variables that favour the pathogen). Only when an agent can defeat the host immunity in a favourable situation does an infection appear; we need to increase our immunity or *vyadhikshamtava* to prevent these disorders.

Role of Oja Vrundhikara and Bala Vrudhikara Dravyas in the prevention of Tuberculosis/Rajayakshama

- 1) Acharya Charaka stated Jeevniya medications, including *jeevak*, *rishabhaka*, *meda*, and *mahameda*, which encourage the development of high-quality bodily tissues and are used to treat *ojas* disorders like *rajayakshma* and *prameha*, among others.^[11]
- 2) It was discovered that combining four significant *Rasayana* medicines, *Guduchi*, *Ashwagandha*, *Amalaki*, and *Tulasi* in equal doses, might enhance both the cellular and humoral aspects of immunity. In addition to targeted therapy, the combination was found to boost immune function and speed up recovery in cancer, multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, chronic wasting disorders, and other immune-compromised illnesses.^[12]
- 3) The purpose of the *Rasayanas* is to increase *Oja* and *Bala*, or vitality and bio strength, together with natural resistance to ageing and disease. Numerous medications, including *Chyawanprash*, are referred to in *Ayurveda* as *Rasayana* and *Ojovardhak* treatments because they are thought to have immunomodulatory properties. It is the most effective *rasayana* and is excellent for treating cough, dysphonia, and hoarseness of voice. It aids in the development of children and is helpful for the old, hurt, and weak. It is a more effective treatment for boosting the immune system, battling germs, and protecting the body from many infections.^[13]
- 4) Acharya Charaka also described the *Balya* medicines, such as *bala*, *Attibala*, *aswagandha*, and *shatavari*, which improve physical toughness by encouraging *ojas*. *Bala* has been seen as an *ojas* action. The body loses its ability to carry out its own natural function in the absence of *ojas*.^[14]

RESULT

After studying data about *Bala*, *Ojas*, and immunity, it could be said that there is a significant correlation between these, and they have similar functions. These are important for protecting the body against various disorders, and increasing *Bala* or *Ojas* by various *Rasayan*, *Vajikaran*, or various *Balya* drugs could help in fighting or preventing diseases like Tuberculosis or *Rajayakshma*.

DISCUSSION

Bala and Ojas^[15]

Normal *Kapha dosha*, which is largely responsible for lubricating and strengthening the body, and *Ojas*, which is a vital energy or bodily component that supports life, are both referred to as "*Bala*." The ultimate and perfect essence of all *dhatu*s is *ojas*. Because of the similarities in their *gunas* and the fact that in its normal stages of functioning, *Kapha* can be a source of strength and resistance to sickness, according to Acharya Charaka, normal *kapha* is sometimes used as a synonym for *ojas*, *bala*, and *vyadhikshamatva*. Acharya Sushruta defined *bala* as the body's capacity to fight against sickness and

used the term *bala* to denote *ojas*. *Ojas* keeps the body in a healthy state when it is present in good quality and an appropriate amount. *Ojovisransa*, *Ojovyapat*, and *Ojokshaya* are *vikriti* of *Ojas* that cause numerous illnesses in our bodies. One such terrible illness that is brought on by *Ojokshaya* is *Rajayakshma*. Numerous causes of *ojakshaya* have been identified in the *Samhita*, including excessive exercise, fasting, worrying, fear, grief, dry, and limited dietary intake, dry beverage consumption, exposure to wind and sunlight, insomnia, excessive excretion of the *kapha*, *shonita*, *shukra*, and *mala*, unfavourable season, or old age.

Vyadhikshamatva, Bala, and Immunity

The word "*Vyadhikshamatav*" has a broad definition in terms of both therapeutic and preventative aspects. Immunity serves as both the body's defence system against disease and a tool for fostering good health. Therefore, immunity can be categorised under *Vyadhikshamatav*. *Sahaja Balam* and innate or inborn immunity are comparable. For instance, Feline distemper is a disease that exclusively affects cats and no other animals.^[16] In the gastrointestinal tract, salivary Lysozyme kills germs. Enzymes in digestive fluids and stomach acid remove hazardous substances or organisms that enter the respiratory system through meals. In the lungs, neutrophils, lymphocytes, macrophages, and natural killer cells fight off germs and viruses^[17], which are comparable to the *Vikaravighata Bhavas*, factors that stop the development of diseases (*Sahaja Balam*). You could compare acquired immunity to *Yuktikrita Balam*. For instance, a person will develop immunity to various diseases after practising *Rasayana Yogas* (*Samskaras* like *Swarnaprashana*, *Jatakarma*, *KarnaVedhana*, *Phala*, *Annaprashana*, etc.).

Ojokshaya is the cause of the terrible illness known as *Rajayakshma*. Thus, by using immunomodulators, or *rasayanas*, we can boost *ojas* in *rajayakshma* patients. Modern science too suggests that people with less immunity are more susceptible for disease like tuberculosis. According to Acharya Charaka, *Asadhya* disorders such as *Vatavyadhi*, *Apasmara*, *Kushtha*, *Shopha*, *Udara*, *Gulma*, *Madhumeha*, and *Rajayakshma* become *Asadhya* in character and should be avoided by the doctor when they are linked to loss of strength and muscular wastage. Therefore, *vyadhikshamtva* is crucial for the therapy of *rajayakshma*. Patients must adhere to a healthy diet regimen for raising the *bala* & *ojas* to recover more quickly and prevent complications.^[18]

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